

Steam-sterilizable cationic nanodiamond–silver composites with enhanced antibacterial activity

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Hydrogenated nanodiamonds (H-NDs) combine high biocompatibility with a positive ζ -potential, yet exhibit only weak and medium-dependent antibacterial effects. Here, we engineer H-ND (median sizes 18 and 125 nm) into Ag-decorated composites (H-ND-Ag) without suppressing their positive surface charge (cationic character) by adsorbing a thin chitosan layer and followed by mild polyethyleneimine-assisted AgNP formation. We evaluate how autoclaving steam sterilization affects the surface chemistry and dispersion of both pristine H-ND and the H-ND-Ag. Autoclaving perturbs the neat H-ND, leading to decreased ζ -potential and eventual aggregation. In contrast, the chitosan–Ag shell preserves the positive charge and long-term colloidal stability of H-ND-Ag. The H-ND-Ag composites suppress the growth of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* at low loadings, matching or exceeding the performance of reported, protein-stabilized ND–Ag benchmarks. The results support a contact-mediated “Ag-patch” delivery mechanism in which carrier size and Ag distribution – rather than surface charge alone – dominate antibacterial efficacy, and establish a protein-free, autoclave-sterilization-compatible route to durable antibacterial nanodiamond formulations.

Introduction

Nanodiamonds (ND) are carbon nanomaterials with distinctive physico-chemical attributes: high specific surface area, tailorable surface chemistry, mechanical robustness, and biocompatibility, that enable applications spanning biomedicine, quantum technologies, catalysis, and environmental remediation.^{1–4} Their optical readouts (e.g., color centers with stable fluorescence, negligible photobleaching), and chemical versatility have further catalyzed interest in ND-based “smart” platforms for imaging, sensing, and delivery.⁵

Despite this promise, reports of intrinsic antibacterial activity of unmodified NDs remain mixed and strongly context-dependent. Media composition, ionic strength, and protein corona formation modulate ND aggregation and surface charge, making a simple mechanistic explanation difficult. For example, colony reductions sometimes observed with *Staphylococci* in salt-rich media have been attributed primarily to heteroaggregation between NDs and bacteria rather than to bactericidal mechanisms, while *E. coli* often shows a negligible response under comparable conditions.^{6,7} Collectively, these observations caution that ND surface chemistry, dispersion state, and test medium are pivotal for interpreting “antibacterial” ND effects.

One robust strategy to move beyond these limitations is to use ND as a tunable carrier for catalytically or photophysically active nanoparticles. ND-Au hybrids exemplify this approach, combining plasmonics for surface – enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) analysis, photoacoustic imaging, and photothermal transduction with ND’s chemical stability and biocompatibility.^{1,8–10} In antimicrobial contexts, ND-Ag

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composites are particularly compelling: immobilizing Ag nanoparticles (AgNPs) on ND can mitigate uncontrolled AgNP aggregation at bacterial surfaces and sustain contact-mediated activity.^{11,12} Chang *et al.* demonstrated that BSA-stabilized ND-Ag (Ag-ND@BSA) achieves low $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) values against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, highlighting an ND-enabled “Ag-patch” delivery effect.¹¹

Charge state is another important parameter. Most published ND composites employ oxidized, negatively charged ND, yet many bacterial cell walls are net negative, suggesting that positively charged carriers could enhance initial adhesion and local dosing via electrostatics. For other nanoparticle families, cationic surfaces accelerate membrane interactions and can lower MICs, whereas anionic analogues often rely more on reactive oxygen species (ROS) pathways.¹³ Positively charged hydrogenated ND (H-ND) are, therefore, attractive carriers: hydrogen termination yields unusual electronic/surface properties, including positive ζ -potential in water, while maintaining ND biocompatibility.¹⁴ However, the intrinsic antibacterial action of H-ND alone is, at best, weak and medium-dependent, and appears markedly inferior to purpose-engineered cationic systems or to ND-Ag hybrids.^{7,15}

Translational deployment further requires validated sterilization. Biologically used colloids must be sterile, yet sterilization can alter nano-surface chemistry and colloidal stability. Ultrafiltration can remove microbes without changing chemistry but is limited by particle size and does not address endotoxins.¹⁶ Gas-phase plasma and UV can oxidize carbon surfaces.^{16,17} Sterilization by autoclaving – the most practical and broadly accepted method – has been reported to modify some carbon nanomaterials while leaving others comparatively intact.^{18,19} For NDs and related carbons, autoclave conditions ($\sim 121^\circ\text{C}$, saturated steam) may shift surface functional groups and ζ -potential, with consequences for dispersion and bio-interactions.^{20,21} In H-NDs specifically, FTIR studies have linked the $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ Fano-type feature (interplay of the diamond phonon and near-surface charge carriers) to surface/electronic states that are sensitive to oxidation; low-temperature oxidation of hydrogenated detonation NDs has been observed starting near $100\text{--}150^\circ\text{C}$.^{22–24} The positive ζ -potential often attributed to H-ND is likewise interpreted through protonation/transfer-doping frameworks rather than idealized, perfectly C-H-terminated surfaces.^{25,26}

In this context, two pragmatic questions motivate this work. Can positively charged H-NDs act as efficient carriers for AgNPs, potentially using electrostatic adhesion, when compared to the more common protein-stabilized, negatively charged ND-Ag constructs?¹⁵ And how does steam sterilization by autoclaving modify H-ND surface chemistry, ζ -potential, and dispersion state, and can a composite architecture buffer these changes without sacrificing antibacterial function?

To address these issues, we prepare hydrogenated HPHT NDs with median sizes of 18 and 125 nm (H-ND18, H-ND125) and positive zeta potential, convert them into still cationic H-ND-Ag composites (H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag,) via a minimal chitosan shell and mild polyethyleneimine (PEI) reduction, and compare neat H-NDs and H-ND-Ag before and after autoclaving.

We correlate DLS/ ζ -potential and FTIR data, including the evolution of C-H and O-H/C=O bands and the $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ Fano-type feature, with transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)-quantified Ag loading, and we quantify antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* via growth curves and MIC. By contrasting our protein-free, cationic H-ND-Ag with literature-reported, protein-stabilized, anionic analogues, we delineate the roles of ND carrier charge, size, and Ag distribution in determining efficacy, and we map how autoclaving influences H-ND colloids versus H-ND-Ag composites. This integrated analysis provides design rules for autoclave sterilization-compatible, protein-free H-ND-Ag nanocomposites that retain colloidal and antibacterial function.

Material and methods

Materials

Hydrogenation of NDs

In the preparation of H-ND, we followed the same procedure reported previously.¹⁴ Briefly, we used commercially available HPHT monocrystalline nanodiamonds – MSY18 with a size range $0\text{--}0.03\ \mu\text{m}$ with a median size of 18 nm and MSY125 with a size range $0\text{--}0.25\ \mu\text{m}$ with a median size of 125 nm (Pureon, Switzerland). First, both ND powders were purified and their surface chemistry homogenized by air annealing treatment at 450°C for 5 h. Subsequently, NDs were hydrogenated by atmospheric-pressure annealing in hydrogen gas at 800°C for MSY18 (further labelled as H-ND18) and 1000°C for MSY125 (further labelled as H-ND125) for 6 h. Water-based colloidal dispersions were prepared by dispersion of 1.0 mg of ND powder in 1.0 mL of deionized water and treated by a rod-type sonicator (Hielscher, UP200s) at 120 W for 1 h.

H-ND-Ag nanocomposites

In the first step, the H-ND were coated with a thin chitosan layer. The suspension of H-ND in deionized H_2O (1 mg NDs/1 mL) was mixed with a solution of chitosan (0.01 % w/w) in 10 mmol HCl in a 3:1 (chitosan solution: NDs suspension) ratio. This suspension was stirred at 60°C for 2 h and then left at room temperature for 2 days. Then, the suspensions were washed with deionized water three times by using centrifugation at $14500 \times g$ for 20 min for H-ND18 and 10 min for H-ND125, and finally re-dispersed in deionized water by the rod-type sonicator for 1 min, yielding chitosan-coated H-ND18 and H-ND125.

In the second step, the AgNPs were formed and anchored to the H-ND-chitosan surface. The 5 mL of H-ND-chitosan suspension was stirred at 100°C for 20 min. Then, a freshly prepared silver nitrate solution was added dropwise into the mixture to a final molar concentration of 0.04 mol/L of AgNO_3 . During the addition of AgNO_3 , the mixture was stirred and kept at 100°C for 10 min in a dark place. Then the 5 mL solution of PEI (0.01 % w/w) in water was added, and stirred at 100°C for another 30 min in the dark. PEI was used as a reducing agent, while keeping the overall cationic character of chitosan and H-ND. Formation

of AgNPs was accompanied by the appearance of a yellow color due to the plasmonic absorption of AgNPs. Such prepared H-ND-Ag samples were washed with deionized water three times by repeated centrifugation at 14500 x g for 20 min for H-ND18-Ag and 10 min for H-ND125-Ag, and finally re-dispersed in deionized water by the rod-type sonicator for 1 min.

Autoclave sterilization process

ND samples were sterilized in an autoclave PS 20 A (Chirana) at a temperature of 121 °C and pressure of 101.5 kPa above atmospheric pressure for 1 h in glass vials. The samples were then stored in dark conditions at 4 °C.

Methods

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and ζ -potential were measured by a Zetasizer Nano (Malvern Panalytical) equipped with a helium-neon laser (633 nm); the scattering angle was 173°. The refractive index of bulk diamond (2.4) and the viscosity of pure water (0.89004 mPa.s at 25 °C) were used. Every sample was measured three times, and each of the three DLS size measurements consisted of 10 runs lasting 10 s. The size values are given as the Z-average, a characteristic size, obtained from the intensity-weighted mean hydrodynamic size. The ζ -potential value was calculated as the average of 3 zeta potential values using the Henry equation. Both DLS and zeta potential measurements were done in a disposable ζ -potential measurement cell.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was measured by a Bruker Vertex 70v spectrometer equipped with a KBr beam splitter and an N₂-cooled MCT detector. 50 μ L of a suspension was drop-casted onto IR-transparent CaF₂ substrates and heated briefly at 60 °C to evaporate the liquid. The measurement chamber was evacuated, ensuring low water vapor and CO₂ partial pressure. All spectra were measured in a transmission regime. Each spectrum represents an average of 128 scans per spectrum collected in the range of 4000–1000 cm⁻¹ at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution.

TEM images were acquired by Tecnai G2 20 (FEI) TEM with a LaB₆ cathode at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. The TEM is equipped with a CCD camera Olympus Veleta. Samples in TEM were inspected on a carbon-coated copper grid, which was immersed in ND colloids before observation.

To quantify the silver content in the nanocomposite suspension, an AAS device (Agilent 280FS) was used, employing a laminar premixed flame generated by burning a mixture of acetylene and air at approximately 2300 °C. The analysis was conducted using a wavelength of 328.1 nm.

Bacterial strains and culture conditions

Gram-positive bacterial strain *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and Gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 were obtained from the Czech collection of microorganisms (CCM, Czechia). Bacterial suspensions were prepared from pure bacterial cultures grown in Tryptone Soy Broth (TSB, Oxoid Ltd., United Kingdom) and were stored in a mixture of TSB and glycerol (25%) at -80 °C. Before the analysis, bacterial

suspensions were inoculated into sterile TSB, incubated for 24 h at 37 °C, and centrifuged (5000 x g, 2 min). Pellets obtained were resuspended to the desired cell density in TSB and used for antimicrobial tests.

Bacterial growth in the presence of ND derivatives

In a sterile microplate (Gama Group, Czechia), H-ND and H-ND-Ag suspensions were first pipetted to a final concentration of 0.1 g/mL, followed by the addition of a bacterial suspension with an optical density (OD) 0.5 McF. The plate was then incubated in the Eon™ Microplate Spectrophotometer (BioTek, US) at 37 °C for 24 h with dual-axis mixing for 3 s before each measurement. Absorbance at wavelength 620 nm was recorded every 30 min for up to 24 h.

Minimal Inhibitory Concentration

ND colloids in appropriate concentration (0.2 g/mL; 0.1 g/mL; 0.05 g/mL; 0.025 g/mL; 0.02 g/mL; 0.01 g/mL; 0.005 g/mL) and bacterial suspension in Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) adjusted to the OD 0.5 McFarland were added to the sterile 96-well microtiter plate (Gama group, Czechia) in a final volume of 150 μ L of fluid in the well. 150 μ L of bacterial suspension was used as a control of bacterial growth, 150 μ L of TSB was used as a blank. Before cultivation, absorbance at 620 nm was spectrophotometrically measured (Tecan, Switzerland). The plate was placed on an orbital shaker with an adhesive surface in an incubator (temperature 37 °C, shaker rotation speed 120 min⁻¹). After 24 h, absorbance measurement at 620 nm was performed. The difference in measured data before and after the cultivation served as an indicator of bacterial viability in the presence of ND. MIC was determined as the lowest concentration of ND, which completely suppressed bacterial growth ($A_{620nm} < 0.01$). The experiments were performed in at least three biological and technical replicates.

TEM – visualization of bacterial cell interaction with ND

The bacterial suspension in water was mixed with the colloidal solution of H-ND-Ag and gently stirred using sterile tweezers. The bacteria were then incubated with the nanoparticles under static conditions for 30 min to allow sufficient interaction, although the antibacterial effect of H-ND-Ag had not yet occurred at this stage. Subsequently, the suspension was diluted by transferring 50 μ L into 500 μ L of dH₂O to reduce the concentration of unbound nanocomposite. A TEM grid was immersed in this diluted suspension for 10 min and then left to air dry.

Results and discussion

Effect of sterilization on H-ND colloidal stability

For all functional materials intended for biological applications and coming into contact with living matter, it is necessary to evaluate how the sterilization process influences their physicochemical properties. We therefore investigated the colloidal stability of both pristine H-ND and AgNP-decorated H-ND and suspensions before and after sterilization by autoclaving at 120 °C for 20 min, which is the most commonly used sterilization protocol.^{20,21} Our results showed a significant effect of the autoclave sterilization on the stability of pristine H-NDs suspensions in water. **Figure 1** shows the time dependence

Figure 1. Time dependence of ζ -potential (black squares) and Z-average particle size (blue circles) for pristine H-ND18 (a) and H-ND125 (b) suspensions at native pH (6–7), supplemented with photos of corresponding H-ND suspensions.

of ζ -potential values and Z-average values for H-ND18 (a) and H-ND125 (b) suspensions at their “native” pH (6–7). Both suspensions initially exhibited high ζ -potentials (> 40 mV) and nearly stable Z-average values over time, consistent with previous reports of good dispersibility and long-term stability.^{14,23} A slow, gradual decrease in ζ -potential was

Figure 2. TEM images of H-ND18 before (a) and after autoclave sterilization (b). TEM images of H-ND125 before (c) and after sterilization (d).

observed during storage, although without an immediate loss of stability. Stock samples were stored in the dark in tightly sealed vessels at room temperature. They were opened only to extract the necessary volumes for measurements, which were discarded after measurement.

Figures 2a and **2b** show ζ -potential and Z-average values for H-ND18 and H-ND125 after sterilization. Immediately after autoclaving, the ζ -potential decreased by approx 20 mV (to \approx 25 mV) compared to freshly prepared suspensions, yet their colloidal stability was still preserved. The ζ -potential was measured immediately after sterilization by autoclaving once the suspension had cooled to room temperature. However, within 20 days, both suspensions underwent aggregation and sedimentation, accompanied by a further decrease in ζ -potential and a stepwise increase in Z-average. This destabilization was consistent across repeated experiments and was visually evident as turbidity and sediment formation (**Figure 2**). DLS and ζ -potential measurements of destabilized

Figure 3. Time dependence of ζ -potential and Z-average particle size for H-ND18 (a) and H-ND125 (b), and photos of corresponding H-ND suspensions after their agglomeration.

suspensions were already strongly influenced by sedimentation. We note that samples stored cool, dark, and with limited air access remained stable for longer, but the overall trend shows that autoclaving markedly compromises the colloidal stability of pristine H-NDs. TEM images (**Figures 3**) support these findings: non-sterilized by autoclaving suspensions (**Figures 3a, 3c**) show well-dispersed nanoparticles, whereas autoclaved ones (**Figures 3b** and **3d**) display pronounced aggregation.

H-ND decorated by Ag nanoparticles and their colloidal stability

H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites were prepared using chitosan, which provided two key functions. First, adsorption of chitosan altered the colloidal stabilization of nanodiamonds, with steric contributions becoming dominant over electrostatic, thus improving dispersibility in aqueous and especially ionic solutions. Second, it facilitated a stable surface for decorating and anchoring of AgNP upon the addition of a reducing agent. Freshly prepared H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag suspensions exhibited ζ -potentials of 36 and 41 mV, respectively. The long-term temporal evolution of ζ -potential and Z-average (**Fig. 4**) shows that both parameters/values remained unchanged for more than one year, with only minor ζ -potential fluctuations that did not lead to aggregation. This

confirms that steric stabilization dominates the colloidal stability of the suspensions.

Polyethyleneimine (PEI) was selected as the reductant because of its mild reduction capability and its cationic character. In contrast to our previous study using anionic PVP, which decreased ζ -potential significantly,¹⁴ PEI avoided charge compensation effects. In contrast to pristine H-ND, the Ag-decorated nanocomposites remained colloidally stable even after autoclaving. We attributed this stability to effective steric

Figure 4. Temporal evolution of ζ -potential and Z-average for H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag supplemented with photos of corresponding H-NDs dispersions/suspensions after their preparation. Note the logarithmic scale of the X axis.

stabilization provided by both chitosan and PEI.

DLS data (**Figures 1 and 4**) indicate that nanocomposites exhibit larger Z-average values than neat H-NDs, partly due to particle enlargement by AgNP decoration and partial aggregation during synthesis. TEM images (**Figure 5**) show AgNP (~20 nm) anchored variably on H-NDs surface, typically 1–10 AgNPs per

nanodiamond. Most often, nanocomposites with 1-2 AgNPs were observed. Noticeably, autoclaving did not significantly alter AgNP size or morphology. Steric stabilization is a well-established concept to prevent nanoparticle aggregation in complex media.²⁸ For nanodiamonds, most reported approaches rely on complex covalent functionalization.^{29–31} Our strategy is simpler: non-covalent adsorption of chitosan stabilizes positively charged H-NDs through a combination of electrostatic interactions, van der Waals forces, and possibly hydrophobic contributions.¹⁴ This non-covalent approach provides excellent stability even after autoclaving and preserves the inherent intrinsic H-ND properties, such as their positive ζ -potential.

Autoclave sterilization effect on H-ND surface chemistry and electronic properties

The DLS and TEM data demonstrated that sterilization leads to ζ -potential reduction and colloidal destabilization of pristine H-NDs. FTIR analysis provides insight into the underlying surface-chemical and electronic changes responsible for this behavior.

Figures 6a and 6b show FTIR spectra of H-ND18 and H-ND125 before and after sterilization, respectively. Before sterilization by autoclaving, both samples displayed strong C–H_x stretching (2800–3000 cm⁻¹) and bending modes (1460 cm⁻¹), a residual weak C=O band at 1720 cm⁻¹, and a broad O–H stretching between 3000–3600 cm⁻¹. A distinct feature at ~1330 cm⁻¹, particularly pronounced in H-ND18, is attributed to Fano-type destructive interference between the zone-center phonons and free carriers in the near-surface layer,²² which is consistent with previously reported charge carrier features/signature in hydrogenated HPHT nanodiamonds.²³ After sterilization, the 1330 cm⁻¹ feature was strongly suppressed, while O–H and C=O bands increased in intensity, indicating partial oxidation of the hydrogenated surface, consistent with earlier studies showing that hydrogenated detonation nanodiamonds begin to oxidize at temperatures as low as 100–150 °C.²⁴ For H-ND18, this 1330 cm⁻¹ feature was much more intense than for H-ND125, reflecting its higher surface-to-volume ratio; yet it was diminished after sterilization, underlining the sensitivity of near-surface free carriers to oxidative modification. The disappearance of the free-carrier signature confirms that sterilization impacts both near-surface electronic states and surface chemistry.

Figure 5. TEM images of H-ND18-Ag nanocomposites, before (a) and after (b) autoclave sterilization, and TEM images of H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites, before (c) and after (d) autoclave sterilization.

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of H-ND18 (a) and H-ND125 (b) before and after the autoclave sterilization. FTIR spectra of H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites before and after autoclave sterilization, shown together with reference FTIR spectra of chitosan and PEI (c)

FTIR spectra of the Ag-decorated nanocomposites (**Figure 6c**) also showed strong signals at $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ before sterilization, though with opposite interference patterns in H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag. The origin of this difference is unclear but may be related to chitosan or AgNP influencing transfer-doping, as suggested in our earlier work.¹⁴ After sterilization by autoclaving, both nanocomposites exhibited more uniform spectra dominated by chitosan features, reflecting surface modification. Peaks at $3150\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-H_x), $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H_x), 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O), and $1315\text{--}1380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O, C-H_x) confirm strong polymer adsorption. From the two polymers involved, PEI and chitosan, the spectra obviously reflect more of the spectral features found in the spectrum of chitosan. This agrees with the previously confirmed adhesion of chitosan on H-ND surface¹⁴ and also the role of PEI that has been used only as a reductant of Ag⁺ ions, added to the already chitosan-coated H-ND dispersion. Possibly due to the cationic nature of both polymers, PEI was not significantly bound to H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag surfaces.

Quantity of silver in suspension (AAS)

The amount of silver in the H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag suspensions was determined by AAS both before and after the autoclave sterilization process to evaluate the amount of Ag attached and possible losses after sterilization. The results are summarized in **Table I**, showing that all the samples contained 400-500 mg/L of Ag. As expected, the H-ND18-Ag sample exhibited slightly higher Ag concentration than the H-ND125-Ag sample, which is consistent with the larger surface area of the smaller H-ND18. After sterilization, both suspensions displayed lower concentrations of silver (6.6% loss for H-ND18-Ag and 9.1% for H-ND125-Ag). We attribute this loss to an electrostatic deposition of the H-ND-Ag to the surface of the sterilization bottle, which is composed of negatively charged SiO₂. Since the

concentration of H-NDs in H-ND-Ag suspensions was 1 mg/mL, the mass ratio of NDs to AgNP is approximately 200:1. This is consistent with the observed Ag loadings and the typical number of AgNPs per nanodiamond observed in TEM analysis.

Tab. I The concentration of silver in the H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites before (fresh) and after autoclave sterilization (sterile). The concentration of H-NDs in the H-ND-Ag suspensions was 1 mg/ml.

Sample	Ag concentration (mg/L)
H-ND18-Ag fresh	498
H-ND18-Ag sterile	465
H-ND125-Ag fresh	471
H-ND125-Ag sterile	428

Effect of H-ND and H-NDs-Ag on Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria

The antibacterial performance of the prepared H-NDs-Ag composites were evaluated using the representative Gram-positive bacterium *S. aureus* and the Gram-negative bacterium *E. coli*, chosen to reflect differences in cell wall composition/structure, cell shape, and size, and charge distribution. Growth curves of both bacterial species were recorded in the presence of pristine H-ND (H-ND18, H-ND125) and the silver-decorated H-ND-Ag (H-ND18-Ag, H-ND125-Ag). The results plotted in **Figure 7** show a clear difference in antibacterial activity between pristine H-NDs and Ag-decorated H-NDs. Both H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag exhibited a pronounced inhibitory effect against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* compared to the control without the addition of NDs. In contrast, among the pristine H-ND, both H-ND18 and H-ND125 induced only mild growth inhibition of *S. aureus*, which is also supported by their differences in their maximum specific growth rates (**Figure 8**).

Figure 7. Growth curves of *E. coli* (EC) (a) and *S. Aureus* (SA) (b) cultivated in the presence of pristine H-ND18 and H-ND125 and Ag-decorated H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites.

This observation is consistent with the limited works reporting weak or negligible antibacterial properties of NDs with a considerable amount of surface C-H_x bonds,^{32,33} yet, to our knowledge, no antibacterial studies on fully H-terminated ND (whether DND or HPHT) have been reported. We show that H-NDs have at most moderate, medium-dependent antibacterial effects rather than robust bactericidal action. In the clearest assay on detonation NDs, Jíra et al. used partially hydrogenated DNDs with a mixed C-H_x and C-O/C=O termination (i.e., only partially hydrogenated surfaces retaining residual oxygen atoms) and observed ~45% CFU reduction of *E. coli* in Mueller-Hinton, with weaker, transient effects in Luria-Bertani likely tied to protein corona formation and ζ-potential changes.³³ By contrast, deliberately cationized ND (quaternized or cationic-polymer-grafted) show clear and more consistent bactericidal/anti-biofilm activity across Gram-positive/negative strains and in polymer matrices that is consistent with membrane-active mechanisms and higher surface charge

density.^{34–37} Consistently with our results reported here, positively charged H-ND (fully or partially hydrogenated) behave as milder, context-sensitive inhibitors, whereas purpose-engineered cationic NDs are more potent. Notably, a strong bactericidal effect has also been linked to partially oxidized, negatively charged ND surfaces,³² underscoring that surface chemistry and charge identity, not simply “positive vs. negative” charge polarity, govern the dominant role. One of the reasons for the observed weak antibacterial performance of pristine H-ND might be their instability in ionic solutions and/or the fast/rapid formation of a protein corona around H-ND particles,³⁸ which is a known phenomenon occurring in protein-rich media.^{32,39,40} TSB medium used here for bacterial cultivation in the presence of NDs contains approximately of 20 g/L proteins, which can readily adsorb to nanoparticle surfaces and alter their colloidal stability and biological activity.

Figure 8. Maximum specific growth rate of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* during the cultivation with the presence of pristine H-ND18 and H-ND125, and H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites.

In this scenario, the binding of H-ND to the bacterial cell is based only on electrostatic attraction between the positively charged surface of H-NDs and the negatively charged bacterial cell wall. Thus, the subtle differences in the effect of H-ND on Gram-positive bacteria than on Gram-negative bacteria can be observed. Gram-positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*, have an accessible high amount of negatively charged teichoic and teichuronic acids in their peptidoglycan layer, and show somewhat greater sensitivity to H-NDs. On the other hand, Gram-negative bacteria possess an outer membrane with lipopolysaccharides (LPS), which carry a negative charge but also act as a steric and permeability barrier, reducing nanoparticle contact. The existence of this dual role has the capacity to reduce actual contact and uptake of H-ND, which can result in a comparatively weaker effect on *E. coli*. Based on maximum specific growth rates, it is clear that H-ND125 exhibited a stronger inhibition effect than H-ND18 on *S. aureus*.

Figure 9. Minimal inhibitory concentration for *E. coli* (a) and *S. aureus* (b) cultivated in the presence of pristine H-ND18 and H-ND125, and Ag-decorated H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites.

Although smaller particles display stronger antimicrobial effects than larger ones, primarily due to their larger surface area^{41–43} the static culture experimental conditions (with mixing performed only 3 s before each measurement) likely promoted the faster sedimentation of larger H-ND125 nanoparticles, as modelled by Hinderliter et al.⁴⁴ So, accelerated deposition increases the likelihood of direct contact with the bacterial surface, which can mimic stronger apparent antibacterial effects of H-ND-125 may appear despite expected its lower intrinsic biological activity.

Next, we focused on the minimal inhibitory concentrations (MICs) determination of H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag composites. From all the tested concentrations (0.005 g/mL; 0.01 g/mL; 0.02 g/mL; 0.025 g/mL; 0.05 g/mL; 0.1 g/mL; 0.2 g/mL), complete bacteria inhibition was observed at concentrations of 0.05 g/mL and higher (**Figure 9**) for both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. In the case of *E. coli* (**Figure 9a**), the inhibition of H-ND125-Ag was noticeably higher than for H-ND18-Ag in the 0.01 – 0.025 mg/ml concentration range, and the onset of

antibacterial activity is not so abrupt. In the case of *S. aureus* (**Fig. 9b**), both H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag perform similarly, with a complete inhibition observed from 0.05 mg/mL and higher.

It can be concluded that both types of prepared composites exhibit significant antibacterial activity, which is dependent on both concentration and bacterial strain. Given the weak antibacterial activity of pristine H-ND18 and H-ND125 alone, we assume that the pronounced antibacterial activity observed in the composites is primarily attributed to the effect of chitosan and silver, with H-ND serving as a carrier with a positively charged surface. In the past, silver has proven to be effective against a wide range of microorganisms,⁴⁵ despite ongoing concerns regarding bacterial resistance.^{12,46} Nevertheless, it appears to be a suitable agent for suppressing pathogens.

Chang et al. first demonstrated the use of 100 nm ND as a carrier for AgNP 15 and reported a negative ζ -potential of the prepared composites. Similar to our study, both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria were investigated so a comparison is relatively straightforward. Compared with Chang et al., who assembled AgNP on poly-L-arginine–modified, acid-oxidized ~100 nm NDs and then stabilized the hybrid by BSA adsorption (Ag-ND@BSA, final $\zeta \approx -50$ mV), our AgNPs immobilized on positively charged hydrogenated NDs (H-ND18-Ag, H-ND125-Ag) were tested without any protein stabilizer.¹⁵ Chang reported MIC = 15 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ Ag for *E. coli* (OD₆₀₀, 18 h) and MBC = 31 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, with sustained kill at 250 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Converting our data to Ag-equivalents, *E. coli* MICs were ~15.9 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for H-ND18-Ag and ~7.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for H-ND125-Ag; for *S. aureus* both composites gave ~15–16 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Thus, despite lacking BSA (and having a net positive charge), our MICs are comparable to Chang's, and for *E. coli* with the larger H-ND carrier, lower by ~2 \times . Together with Chang's observation that their most active hybrid was net negative due to BSA, these results support a local Ag-patch/dispersion effect (carrier size and Ag loading/distribution) as the primary determinant of potency, with surface charge mainly facilitating initial contact.¹⁵ Interestingly, the MIC results revealed that the Gram-positive bacterium *S. aureus* was less susceptible to both H-ND18-Ag and H-ND125-Ag, requiring higher concentrations for growth inhibition compared to *E. coli*, which contrasts with the behaviour observed for pristine H-NDs. In this scenario, multiple factors probably contributed to these outcomes. In this case, chitosan is also cationic and can enhance the binding to the negatively charged cell wall of bacteria.⁴⁷ Chitosan, present in the form of a thin shell on the H-ND surface, may also contribute to the antibacterial properties through its own cationic and membrane-interactive properties.¹⁴ The antibacterial effect of chitosan⁴⁸ is primarily attributed to ionic and hydrophobic interactions that cause structural damage and increased membrane permeability. Gram-negative bacteria tend to be more sensitive due to their higher hydrophilicity and charge density, which enhances the membrane disruption. Moreover, silver ions have stronger effects on Gram-negative bacteria compared to Gram-positive bacteria, as documented in several studies.^{49–51} This synergistic effect of chitosan and Ag⁺ ions may enhance the destabilization of the membrane

together with the disruption of multiple intracellular targets, particularly in *E. coli*, compared to *S. aureus*.

To better understand the local interactions between the nanocomposites and bacterial cells, TEM analysis was performed after 30 min of incubation. This time was selected on the growth curve dynamics (**Figure 7**) and preliminary TEM observations: after 30 min of exposure, the nanocomposites were already interacting with the bacterial cell walls, but cell death had not yet occurred; in contrast, after 3 hours of contact,

Figure 10. TEM image showing interactions between H-ND-Ag nanocomposites and bacterial cells: H-ND18-Ag in contact with the cell wall of *S. aureus* (a) and *E. coli* (b), and H-ND125-Ag in contact with the cell wall of *S. aureus* (c) and *E. coli* (d).

intact bacteria were no longer observed on the TEM grid and only cellular fragments were observed (data not shown). **Figure 10a** shows three *S. aureus* cocci interacting with H-ND18-Ag. The cell walls appear intact, suggesting that significant structural damage has not yet occurred at this early time point. Small dark aggregates on the bacterial surface indicate initial attachment. The surrounding medium appears relatively homogeneous, with no evident signs of cellular lysis, although localized accumulation of AgNP and ND aggregates at the bacterial cell is visible. The bacterial cell wall reveals some irregularities, possibly due to structural damage induced by AgNP. **Figure 10b** depicts clusters of H-ND18-Ag in contact with the cell wall of *E. coli*. Here, the outer membrane of *E. coli* appears partially damaged. **Figure 10c** shows H-ND125-Ag nanocomposites in contact with the cell wall of *S. aureus*. The nanodiamonds exhibit their characteristic angular morphology with sharp-edged formations. Darker regions again indicate AgNPs immobilized on the ND surface. The presence of structural irregularities or possible damage in the *S. aureus* cell wall suggests that H-ND125-Ag interaction may compromise bacterial integrity. In **Figure 10d**, the interaction between *E. coli* and H-ND125-Ag is shown, revealing the structural damage, indicating membrane disruption.

Conclusions

This study investigates the impact of steam sterilization on the surface and colloidal stability of hydrogenated HPHT nanodiamonds (H-NDs), their subsequent modification into AgNP-bearing H-ND nanocomposites, and the resulting antibacterial activity against Gram-negative *E. coli* and Gram-positive *S. aureus*. We demonstrate that positively charged H-ND serve as effective carriers for AgNPs, yielding long-term stable, autoclave-resilient dispersions when protected by a minimal, non-covalent chitosan shell. Pristine H-ND alone exhibits only mild and medium-dependent antibacterial activity. The H-ND-Ag composites achieve MIC values of ~ 0.025 – 0.05 mg mL⁻¹ (≈ 7.5 – 16 μ g mL⁻¹ Ag), with H-ND125-Ag outperforming H-ND18-Ag against *E. coli*.

FTIR and colloidal measurements indicate that steam sterilization induces surface modifications of pristine H-NDs (surface chemistry and electronic properties), suppressing the diamond-associated ~ 1330 cm⁻¹ feature and increasing O–H/C=O bands, consistent with surface changes (partial surface oxidation and/or desorption). This was accompanied by a decrease in the positive ζ -potential and gradual aggregation upon storage. By contrast, the chitosan/AgNP shell maintained a positive ζ -potential, narrow hydrodynamic size distributions (DLS), and provides strong Ag retention, sustaining colloidal stability and antibacterial performance.

Our findings, together with the literature reference values, suggest that antibacterial efficacy is primarily influenced by nanodiamond carrier size, Ag content/distribution, and steric stabilization, while the positive surface charge of H-NDs facilitates initial bacterial contacts. This work establishes a protein-free, autoclave-compatible strategy/approach for preparing antibacterial nanodiamond–silver nanocomposites, and provides design guidelines for future optimization of Ag dose, polymer-shell architecture, and medium conditions toward strain-selective or application-specific performance.

Author contributions

Katerina Kolarova: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Interpretation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. **Hana Stiborova:** Formal analysis, Data curation, Interpretation, Writing – review and editing. **Simona Lencova:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Maksym Bilozerskyi:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Alexander Kromka:** Supervision, Validation, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review and editing. **Stepan Stehlik:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

Data are available at the Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18503631)

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